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Deliverable

D8.8 - Zero_HiddenHunger_EU

Practice Abstract – 1

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Zero_HiddenHunger_EU

Practice Abstract – 1

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Revision history

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Executive Summary

- This Deliverable report (D8.8, lead UCC) presents AGRI-EIP Practice Abstract 1 of the Zero_HiddenHunger_EU project.
- The purpose of this AGRI-EIP Practice Abstract is to enable knowledge exchange and dissemination of the results of the project in a concise and easy understandable manner for practitioners.
- AGRI-EIP Practice Abstract 1 provides information about the project including background and context, objectives, a short summary and expected outcomes.
- Details of the submission of AGRI-EIP Practice Abstract 1 through the appropriate channels are outlined in this report.
- Two further AGRI-EIP Practice Abstracts (numbers 2 and 3) will be produced in the lifetime of the project, as Deliverables D8.9 and D8.10 respectively.

Section 1 – AGRI-EIP Practice Abstract

Overview of AGRI-EIP Practice Abstract

AGRI-EIP Practice Abstract 1 (PA1) of the Zero_HiddenHunger_EU project is a public-facing piece of informational text, aimed at enabling knowledge exchange and dissemination of the results of the project in a concise and easily understandable manner for practitioners.

PA1 provides information about the project including background and context, objectives, a short summary and expected outcomes. It is presented to align with the EIP-AGRI common format.

PA1 is herein submitted as Deliverable D8.8, led by the project's coordinating organisation, University College Cork. It is intended to remain publicly available.

Details of PA1 submission

The associated .xlsx file in respect of Practice Abstract 1 was provided via email to the following email address on 25 June 2024:

AGRI-EIP-PRACTICE-ABSTRACTS@ec.europa.eu

The Zero_HiddenHunger_EU Project Officer and Policy Officer were included by way of cc on this email communication.

An abridged version of the submitted Practice Abstract containing:

1. Short title in English, and;
2. Summary for practitioners in English

is included on pages 6-7 below.

Further Practice Abstracts

During the lifetime of the project, two further Practice Abstracts will be submitted as deliverables, namely:

- AGRI-EIP Practice Abstract 2 representing Deliverable D8.9, due in month 32 (August 2026). It will provide an overview of the findings from the project's key objective no. 1 – True prevalence of micronutrient deficiencies in Europe.
- AGRI-EIP Practice Abstract 3 representing Deliverable D8.10, due in month 48 (December 2027). It will provide an overview of the findings from the project's key objective no. 2 – Food-based solutions to ensure adequate supply of vitamins and minerals from sustainable diets.

Practice "abstract" 1:

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Short title in English

Tackling micronutrient malnutrition and hidden hunger to improve health in the EU

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc.). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Micronutrient (MN) deficiency (also known as 'Hidden Hunger') afflicts European society, putting human development and health at risk due to inadequate mineral and vitamin intake. Eradication of hidden hunger in Europe requires data on the true prevalence of MN deficiencies, and their associated health costs and, using these data, proposals for prevention that are context-specific, food-first, sustainable and cost-effective, supported by the evidence. Thus, within the first 30 months of the project, Zero_HiddenHunger_EU expects to provide: 1) A credible estimate of the true prevalence of MN deficiency in European populations for the first time and quantify the magnitude of the public health problem of hidden hunger, particularly among high-risk population subgroups; 2) Estimates of the degree of inadequate intakes of key MNs, and 3) Estimates of health costs associated with MN deficiencies in Europe for the first time. By the end of the project, Zero_HiddenHunger_EU expects to 4) Present food-first, sustainable and cost-effective approaches for eradication of MN deficiencies in Europe, 5) Predict, and compare, the cost effectiveness of these proposed dietary-based mitigation strategies, and 6) Provide new insight into the bioavailability of key MNs in the context of the shift toward more plant-based diets for sustainability and health reasons. Overall, the project seeks to empower policymakers, practitioners, and other end-users to eradicate deficiencies across European populations, based on evidence derived from advanced scientific approaches. They will also gain actionable insights leading to tailored solutions in specific contexts, whether public health advice or food formulation, supporting equitable access to essential MNs and improving public health.

Short title in native language

See Short title in English (above).

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

See Short summary for practitioners in English (above).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc.). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Contact Details

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